

The Problem of the Attitude to the Concept in Cognitive Linguistics, Linguoculturology and Linguopsychology

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Abstract: the anthropocentric paradigm, which took its first steps in the last quarter of the XX century, became one of the leading fields in linguistic research from the beginning of the new century. Cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology are recognized as the leading directions of the anthropocentric paradigm, embodying the latest achievements of the field and increasingly strengthening their status as independent directions. These fields intersect with psycholinguistics at many points. This article discusses one of the main categories common to these directions, an important object of study - the concept. Although the term concept has been interpreted by many scientists, different sources give different opinions about its definition, content, and scope. In this study, within the framework of the concept, the views of linguists were studied, their reactions to different issues were expressed, and general conclusions were stated. Research methods such as comparison, synthesis, induction, deduction, generalization and abstraction were used in this process.

Key words: cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, psycholinguistics, concept.

Introduction

In addition to linguistics, the term concept can be found in various fields such as mathematics, cultural studies, logic, psychology, philosophy, and in each of them this concept has its own meaning and function. In particular, in linguistics, the concept is used as one of the forms of manifestation of knowledge about existence in general; The definitions given to it and the relations expressed in such fields as psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology are different. The multifaceted nature of the term also causes confusion as it is interpreted in several fields at the same time. The beginning of consistent scientific research on this topic is associated with the names of English scientists J. Miller, N. Chomsky, A. Newell, R. Jackendoff, G. Lakoff. The attention of the scientific community to this topic increased as a result of their extensive discussion of the concept in their lectures and works. The term concept was originally interpreted only in the cognitive sphere. The concept was the main topic in the journal "Cognitive Linguistics" and the monograph series "Cognitive Linguistics Research", which were published as a result of efforts to unite cognitive research within a single discipline under a single "umbrella". As a result of the development of science, the term concept, which was applied to various fields such as linguoculturology, psycholinguistics, began to be defined in an interdisciplinary way. As a result, controversial opinions began to arise among scientists on issues such as the definition, essence, and scope of this term. These debates and different views cause many problems and confusion in the world of science, especially for young scientists. In order to provide a suitable solution to these debates, the works of scientists who conducted research within the framework of the concept in Uzbek and world linguistics were studied, and using research methods such as comparison, synthesis, induction, deduction, generalization and abstraction, a suitable solution to the problem and a final definition of the term were given.

Theoretical Basis

The term concept (Latin "conceptus" means "notion") was first introduced to science in the Middle Ages by philosophers such as U. Hobbes, P. Abelard and U. Occam. They interpreted the concept as a

universal factor summarizing the signs of things and embodied by the mind for its internal use, which contains important and relevant information. In the linguistic literature, this concept began to appear in the first half of the 20th century. This term was first used in 1928 in an article by the Russian linguist S.A. Askaldov-Alekseyev. However, until the 1970s, it was not studied as a separate research object as one of the explanatory topics.

Taking into account the multifaceted nature of the concept, V.A. Maslova gives the following definitions, paying attention to the linguistic, cognitive, pragmatic, cultural, sociological aspects that are considered necessary in its interpretation (Maslova, 2008, p. 37):

1. the expression of the minimal units of human experience in the ideal imagination, expressed through words and having a field structure;
2. the main unit of knowledge processing, storage and transmission;
3. that it has its own dynamic limits and certain functions;
4. having a social character, manifesting its pragmatic aspects based on its associative field;
5. the main link of culture.

A different approach to such a concept can be seen in V.I. Karasik's studies. According to him, the concept is primarily based on language, that is, it reflects the characteristics of an object, a symbol, an event-process. Secondly, the concept is a cognitive-psychological unit, in which fragments of meaning appear in such forms as a script, frame, *geshtalt*. According to the last approach, the concept is an evaluator of cultural values that has a deductive nature as a product of ethical-esthetic categories (Karasik, 2009, p. 24).

The dictionary meaning and scientific definition of the concept term, which has been used in Uzbek national linguistic literature since the 1990s, has been interpreted in several ways by Uzbek linguists. Scientists such as N. Mahmudov, Sh. Safarov, A. Mamatov, D. Khudoyberganova, D. Lutfullayeva expressed different views on this matter.

Professor Sh. Safarov takes a cognitive approach to the essence of the concept and describes it as "a mental structure formed in the process of knowing", and also emphasizes that it simultaneously manifests national views: "Researching the cognitive activity of a person in the creation of a text serves to shed light on the way of thinking specific to the Uzbek mentality. After all, the thought conceptualized in the text can be ethnic in some cases (Safarov, 2008, p. 245).

We can see the same interpretation in Professor N. Mahmudov: "...the concept is a mental concept related to thinking, but it is quite controversial to consider it as a phenomenon completely free from national and cultural elements (Mahmudov, 2017, p. 60)".

D. Khudoyberganova also recognized that the concept is, first of all, a product of the cognitive process: "The concept is an abstraction. It cannot be observed directly. This phenomenon, which is related to the cognitive activity of a person, can be determined through its correlates in language," he says. The scientist also draws attention to the fact that it is a multi-layered mental structure that is not devoid of psychological and cultural characteristics: "The concept ... is a structure that manifests psychological, cognitive-semantic and linguo-cultural aspects. After all, the fact that the concept is described as an object of cognitive and linguo-cultural studies is also evidence of this." Improving these views, the scientist gives the following separate definitions of the concept in the cross-section of fields:

1. In cognitive linguistics, it is a unit of the information system that reflects the mental and spiritual capabilities of the human mind, its knowledge and experience.
2. In linguoculturology, it is a unity of collective consciousness, which has the characteristics of mentality and linguistic expression, and is distinguished by its ethno-cultural identity.

3. In psycholinguistics, it is a mobile perceptive-cognitive-affective structure that arises in the cognitive and communication activities of a person and obeys the laws of his psyche (Khudoyberganova, 2015, p. 25).

Results

As a result of studies, it is appropriate to make the following points about the concept.

A concept is a quantum of knowledge in the mind about perceived concrete and abstract, inner and outer existence. The concept reflects a person's negative, positive and neutral attitude towards a certain thing or event. When a person hears, sees, smells, tastes, feels or imagines something, if it is familiar to him, he immediately remembers the related knowledge, ideas, and experiences gained as a result of understanding the world around him during his past life, and all of them, combined, form the "biogenetics" of this concept.

In the mind of each person, there is a separate quantum field - conceptual field about the perceived uniqueness of the world in which he lives, and these "props in the field" are enriched and perfected throughout his life. A number of factors influence it in this process. However, no stage in this perfection can be evaluated as an ideal final state. Because the concept is an unfathomable that reveals new facets as it dives like the ocean. Also, its life cycle does not end with one human life.

Just as no two people are the same in society, it is far from possible for two people to have the same conceptual space at the same time. After all, based on education, experience, knowledge, skills, qualifications, etc., everyone looks at the world with their own eyes and understands it in their own way. In this way, universal concepts are formed on the basis of the individual concept, existence and repetition of the central, dominant themes in the personal evaluation, group (national) and general universal recognition of all nations and people. In this process, the interpreter moves between consciousness and existence as one of the experiences that represent the concept. Just like nothing stays the same forever, the concept is always moving and changing, over time the meaning it carries is enriched and developed, and some of them may even fall out of our speech. In this process, a human society with a linguistic identity serves as one of the important products that ensure the viability of the concept. The concept appears in each language and culture in its own way.

Discussion

As can be seen from the definitions given above, when it comes to the essence and scope, some scientists interpret the concept with specific features in the field of application, while another group of scientists put forward their views that the concept reflects the views of all fields by integrating and generalizing.

However, these definitions, which differ from each other in form, in our opinion, are not the basis for giving the concept the quality of lexeme in the linguistic framework, but are the result of approaching the single essence in different ways. In the process of conceptual analysis, it cannot be denied that regardless of which method is placed in the center of analysis, one complements the other. The only aspect that should be taken into account is that when one concept prevails in essence, the other weakens. In other words: "Considering that the concept is large-scale and multi-level, based on the object of research, the priority level of a certain concept can be determined, that is, for some research, the psychological or psycholinguistic level of the issue is the priority, for another, etymological, ethnographic, and for others, cultural, linguocultural aspects may be in the focus of attention (Krasavsky, 2000, p. 78).

It is known that all the sciences that are defined as a separate object of concept research are network fields formed at the intersection of disciplines, and the study of an object in the integration of sciences expands the perception of the object. It is also clear that researching from all sides without clearly defining the scope of the object leads to various confusions and increases the possibility that the essence

of the subject being studied will not be fully revealed. Also, there are certain difficulties in evaluating the object and subject of science. This, firstly, distracts the linguist from his main object - language; secondly, it causes signs of dilettantism in his research (Kasimova, 2021, p. 26). For this reason, although the study of the factor of the person who creates and perceives the text requires approaching the object of research from various aspects, in particular, from the semantic, psychological, pragmatic, cognitive, and linguocultural point of view, in conceptual studies, the researcher recognizes that the concept is the indivisible whole of the knowledge of the whole being (all fields) in thinking, and defines only one of its edges as the object of research, and based on the chosen object of each direction representative it is appropriate to approach it from the point of view of science.

As a result of studies, it should be mentioned that, as Professor N. Mahmudov noted in one of his articles, the term concept has the most definitions, but these and related concepts have not yet been interpreted with a unanimous general explanation. The reason for this is perfectly justified by the scientists as follows: "There is no complete answer to these questions yet, and it is doubtful that it will be found." There are certainly reasons for suspicion. First of all, it should not be forgotten that the concept is a very abstract phenomenon, the "mental structure" at its core does not have any material appearance, but is an imaginary structure formed in the process of mental perception (Safarov, 2010, p. 185-188)". The fact that there is no single description of the concept is characterized by the fact that it is a complex, comprehensive structure from a social, psychological, and cultural point of view; concepts are based on various associations, emotions, subjective assessment, national image and connotations specific to a particular culture. The multifacetedness of the concept is explained by the fact that its field covers both rational and emotional, concrete and abstract, universal and ethnic, national and individual concepts at the same time.

Conclusion

In short, a concept is a generalization of images, concepts, knowledge, experience, and hypotheses embedded in the essence of a specific language unit. The concept is a multifaceted, integrative phenomenon, in which the logical-linguistic-epistemological levels are united at the same time, and a general image, a summary assessment is determined about a certain thing-phenomenon, sign-property, action-state realized in nature and society. The concept reflects the result of interaction between a number of factors and thinking, such as national customs, life experience, image, values, national tradition, religion, ideology, folklore.

The concept is a general and at the same time a private phenomenon for every person and every society. The essence of what it means is enriched and polished based on life knowledge and experiences. As experience and outlook become richer, the scope of the information content of the concept expands, and thus the concept can manifest itself in all ways.

References:

1. Jackendoff R. What is a Concept, that a Person May Grasp It? *Mind & language*. – 1989. – Т. 4. – №. 1-2. – P. 68-102.
2. Сафаров Ш. Когнитив тилшунослик. –Жиззах: Сангзор, 2006. – Б. 20.
3. Маслова В. А. Введение в когнитивную лингвистику. –М.: Флинта: Наука, 2006. – С.37
4. Карасик В.И. Языковые ключи. – М.: Гнозис, 2009. – С.24.
5. Сафаров Ш. Когнитив тилшунослик. – Жиззах. Сангзор, 2006. 21-bet.
6. Сафаров Ш. Прагмалингвистика. –Т., 2008. Б. 245
7. Mahmudov N. Til tilsimi tadqiqi. –Т.: Mumtoz so‘z. 2017. 60-bet.
8. Худойберганава Д. Матнинг антропоцентрик тадқиқи. – Тошкент: Фан, 2013. – Б.13.

9. Худойбергана Д. Лингвокультурологик терминларнинг қисқача изоҳли луғати. –Т.:Turon zamin ziyo, 2015. Б. 25.
10. Красавский Н.А. Концепт “Zorn” в пословично-поговорочном фонде немецкого языка. // Теоретическая и прикладная лингвистика. Выпуск 2. Язык и социальная среда. – Воронеж. Изд-во ВГТУ, 2000. – С.78
11. Қосимова М. Ўзбек ва инглиз тилларида бахтлилик ва бахтсизлик концептуал бинар оппозицияси. Филология фанлари бўйича фалсафа док. (Doctor of Philosophy) илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган дисс. –Андижон. 2021. –В. 26
12. Сафаров Ш. «Концепт» ҳодисаси ҳақида//Систем-структур тилшунослик муаммолари (Н.Қ.Турниёзов таваллудининг 70 йиллигига бағишланган Республика илмий-назарий конференцияси материаллари).–Самарқанд, 2010. –Б.185-188